

ORGANIZATIONAL AND LEGAL BASIS OF IMPLEMENTING ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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ABSTRACT

This thesis discusses the organizational and legal issues of introducing artificial intelligence in the Republic of Uzbekistan. At the same time, the needs that led to the adoption of these documents, their main goals and objectives, scope and practical significance are analyzed. The role of these documents in the development of artificial intelligence technologies, their application in the economy and social spheres, as well as their role in ensuring legal stability and security are also discussed in detail.

Introduction. In recent years, artificial intelligence technologies have been developing at an unprecedented pace worldwide, penetrating deeply into the economy, education, medicine, law, and many other areas; this process has led to the development of the digital economy and innovative technologies in Uzbekistan being considered one of the top priorities of state policy.

From a scientific point of view, the widespread introduction of such technologies creates the need to regulate them legally, strengthen them with clear norms and rules, and ensure the principles of human rights, data security, and transparency. “Artificial intelligence is an important element of the fourth industrial revolution. Its rapid development and expansion of practical application require the “inclusion” of this phenomenon in the field of law. Regulating public relations in one way or another related to the development and application of artificial intelligence is a complex task, and experts have different views on which areas and activities should be regulated, and the proposed approaches to regulation differ significantly in different countries”[1]. The need to introduce these approaches into legislation, that is, to improve the organizational and legal framework of artificial intelligence, reflects the relevance of our research work.

Main part. Although the legal norms regulating artificial intelligence in Uzbekistan are still at the stage of formation, the prospects of this area in the national legal system are becoming increasingly clear and relevant, since the process of modern digital reforms requires updating not only technological, but also legal frameworks; in this process, the “Digital Uzbekistan - 2030” strategy adopted by the state, decisions on the development of the e-government system, as well as current

legislative norms on data collection, processing and protection, serve as the foundation for the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies. M.Yakubov noted that the legal framework regulating artificial intelligence is not yet sufficient to create a complete, comprehensive and special legal regime for artificial intelligence; Therefore, they propose the following as important steps for the future:

first, to establish the definition, classification and legal status of artificial intelligence at the national legislative level,

secondly, to introduce the principles of transparency and accountability in the use of artificial intelligence algorithms,

thirdly, to develop clear standards for data security, privacy protection and cybersecurity,

fourthly, they emphasize the need to strengthen the mechanism for human review of decisions made on an artificial basis in law.

At the same time, economic and legal measures such as supporting the national innovation ecosystem, providing tax incentives to local software developers, and opening artificial intelligence laboratories on the basis of public-private partnerships will also serve the rapid development of artificial intelligence.

All this is necessary not only to consolidate technological achievements on a legal basis, but also to ensure that Uzbekistan takes a strong place in the international digital economy. Because if artificial intelligence is not legally regulated, then in the future it will be of strategic and historical importance for our country to develop a single national concept for artificial intelligence, clearly defining the stages of development of the industry, regulatory models and priority areas, gradually supplementing the legislation and establishing a system of integral cooperation between state bodies, scientific institutions and the business sector. Because in time, artificial intelligence will not only improve the quality of services, but will also begin to act as a reliable partner in public administration, the judiciary and civil relations; and then our laws will become a foundation that can withstand the test of time, combining technological thinking and legal wisdom[2].

We will talk about the adopted regulatory and legal documents aimed at regulating the field of artificial intelligence in the Republic of Uzbekistan. This section analyzes the needs that led to the adoption of these documents, their main goals and objectives, scope and practical significance. It also discusses in detail the role of these documents in the development of artificial intelligence technologies, their application in the economy and social spheres, as well as their role in ensuring legal stability and security.

First of all, according to the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5234 dated August 26, 2021 “On measures to introduce a special regime for the application of artificial intelligence technologies”, it is established to create a special regime for the development of innovative projects in the field of artificial intelligence technologies in Uzbekistan[3].

The main purpose of the special regime is to create favorable conditions for the implementation of experimental research, software products and services based on artificial intelligence.

The content of this document is aimed at legally strengthening the activities of legal services in the Republic of Uzbekistan, organizing them on the basis of a unified system and increasing their efficiency, which defines the main tasks, areas of activity, rights and obligations, management and control mechanisms of legal services in state bodies, economic management bodies, local government bodies, enterprises, institutions and organizations.

Another important aspect of the document is the establishment of mechanisms for regular monitoring and analysis of the activities of legal services, the use of the results of this process in improving legislation. Thus, it serves to increase the real efficiency of legal services, ensure compliance with the rule of law in state bodies and other organizations, and prevent legal errors. The main directions of the document are as follows:

1. creating conditions for independent and professional activity of legal services by clearly defining their powers and responsibilities;
2. improving the quality of legal documents, ensuring their legality and practical effectiveness;
3. developing the material, technical and human resources capacity of legal services;
4. organizing the activities of legal services in state and economic management bodies, as well as other entities, on the basis of a unified methodology;
5. introducing a regular monitoring system for assessing and analyzing the activities of legal services;
6. introducing modern technologies and best practices in the development of legal services.

The second important regulatory and legal document, Resolution No. 717 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 29, 2021, approved the Regulation on the procedure for establishing a special regime to support artificial intelligence technologies and establishing its activities in order to ensure the implementation of Presidential Resolution No. PQ-5234.

This regulation establishes the procedure for using the special regime and organizing the activities of its participants, the tasks of the working body, registration of applicants, exemptions from current legislative norms during the period of pilot projects, as well as comprehensive support for participants, the application of privileges and preferences to them. According to the resolution, the Ministry of Information and Communications Development, the Ministry of Economic Development and Poverty Reduction and Employment, and the Ministry of Innovative Development are required to establish a special regime within one month and conduct explanatory work in the media about its essence. According to this resolution, the REGULATION on the procedure for establishing a special regime to support artificial intelligence technologies and establishing its activities was approved[4], according to which, “a special legal regime aimed at creating the necessary organizational and legal conditions for legal entities and scientific organizations engaged in the implementation of pilot and testing work based on artificial intelligence technologies, the development of software products and the provision of services, and facilitating legal relations arising in the process of piloting and implementing software products” is called a special regime.

A number of privileges and preferences are established for participants in the special regime, including: the privileges granted to IT park residents will also apply to them if they meet the requirements specified in Resolution No. 589 of the Cabinet of Ministers of July 15, 2019; expenses incurred for improving the qualifications or retraining of employees will be reimbursed by the state in accordance with the procedure established by Presidential Resolution No. PQ-4862 of October 13, 2020; information and documents necessary for the implementation of pilot projects, but not containing state secrets or other confidential information protected by law, as well as declassified personal information, will be obtained from ministries, departments and organizations; the list of documents required to obtain documents of a permitting nature will be reduced by the authorized

state body, the established payment amounts will be halved, and the requirements and conditions for carrying out this activity will be established in a simplified manner.

At the same time, the Resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 475 dated July 31, 2021 “On the Organization of the Activities of the Research Institute for the Development of Digital Technologies and Artificial Intelligence” was adopted, on the basis of which the Research Institute for the Development of Digital Technologies and Artificial Intelligence was established on the basis of the Scientific and Innovative Center for Information and Communication Technologies at the Tashkent University of Information Technologies named after Muhammad al-Khwarizmi and the Scientific and Practical Centers for Intellectual Software Systems at the National University of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek[5].

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-358 dated October 14, 2024 “On Approval of the Strategy for the Development of Artificial Intelligence Technologies” is an important document aimed at the systematic development of the artificial intelligence sector in the country, which approves the strategy for 2024-2026 and the plan of measures for its implementation[6].

This document identifies specific projects aimed at introducing artificial intelligence into various areas, such as digital technologies, healthcare, science and innovation, their implementation deadlines, and responsible ministries and departments. The resolution also indicates the sources of financing for the projects, provides for the cooperation of the Ministries of Digital Technologies, Higher Education, Science and Innovation, Health and other interested departments, and regular reporting on the implementation of the projects.

Also, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 425 dated July 10, 2025 can be recognized as an important practical step in the field of digital economy and artificial intelligence. By this resolution, the “Center for the Development of Artificial Intelligence and Digital Economy” (Center) was established within the Ministry of Digital Technologies[7]. According to it, the main goal of the Center is to develop artificial intelligence technologies, as well as coordinate and implement scientific research in this area. One of the most important areas of the Center’s activity is to study the needs of state bodies and business entities in artificial intelligence and propose solutions to them. The table attached to the document lists a number of specific projects planned to be implemented by the Center.

For example, in September 2025, it was indicated that the project “Development of artificial intelligence-based digital medical assistant software designed to automate and support clinical decision-making and improve the quality of medical care” will be completed. Also, the development of technical documentation for the project “Detection of minor violations (smoking, crossing an unmarked roadway) using computer vision as a test” is scheduled for December 2025.

The system “Formation of a data set for the “Uzbek language corpus” based on artificial intelligence technology” is planned to be completed in February 2026, while the system “Introduction of the function of automatic assignment and tracking of tasks, detection of delays and reminders of upcoming deadlines in the Interdepartmental Document Management System using artificial intelligence” is planned to be completed in November 2026. Special attention is also paid to the issue of personnel, and it is planned to organize online courses to improve the skills of 100 employees of state agencies. The center is organized in the form of a state institution, its activities are financed from the state budget, sponsorship donations, international grants and other sources.

At the same time, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 140 dated August 21, 2025 “On additional measures to increase the level of access to justice through the introduction

of artificial intelligence technologies into the activities of courts and to improve the material and technical support of the judicial system” reflects the following goals.

The following are the priority goals for the coming years to introduce artificial intelligence technologies into the activities of courts and accelerate the processes of digitization, as well as create favorable conditions for citizens and business entities in courts:

- (a) to gradually transfer the conduct of cases to a fully electronic form based on the concept of “Digital Court” in order to abandon the paper form of court proceedings;
- (b) to increase the range of interactive electronic services provided to citizens and business entities, to obtain copies of court documents, to familiarize themselves with court cases, to determine the relevance of the application to the court and the relevance of the trial, to create the possibility of calculating court costs using artificial intelligence, as well as to maintain an electronic register of sources and content prohibited by the court;
- (v) to create the necessary technical infrastructure for the introduction of artificial intelligence technologies into the activities of the courts, as well as to take measures to improve the regulatory and legal framework in this area;
- (g) to develop and implement a judicial documents archive module based on the information systems of the Supreme Court;
- (d) to conduct scientific research in the direction of "Cyber Law" on the digitization of court activities, as well as to continuously improve the digital literacy and skills of judges and court staff;
- (j) to increase the efficiency of economic courts by optimizing their structure and forming a unified judicial practice;
- (z) To gradually organize courtrooms based on the concept of “Digital Court” and create comfortable and modern conditions for the population and judges, as well as strengthen the social protection of judges and court employees[8].

In our opinion, as a result of the introduction of artificial intelligence into the judicial system, tasks such as the complete digitization of court activities and the control of electronic documents in the judicial process using artificial intelligence have been set. Also, as a result of this decree, artificial intelligence began to be studied as a separate field of law. In particular, the direction of cyber law was established as a separate field of law that studies artificial intelligence.

The Presidential Decree of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. 189 dated October 22, 2025 “On Additional Measures for the Further Development of Artificial Intelligence Technologies” set the following goals and objectives for the further development of artificial intelligence:

- (a) by the end of 2026, implement at least 100 projects for the widespread introduction of artificial intelligence technologies in state administration bodies, the social sphere and economic sectors;
- (b) by the end of 2030, attract foreign investments in the amount of more than 1 billion US dollars in the development of modern artificial intelligence infrastructure;
- (v) starting from the 2026/2027 academic year, include topics on teaching artificial intelligence technologies in the curricula and textbooks of the general secondary education and higher education system;

(g) Launching 15 artificial intelligence laboratories in higher education institutions operating in the country by the end of 2026.

According to our firm, this decree has determined the implementation of artificial intelligence in all areas of our society. It has also been determined that artificial intelligence laboratories will be established in all areas of artificial intelligence science and that topics on teaching artificial intelligence technologies will be included in the curriculum of higher education institutions.

Conclusion. Having analyzed the introduction of artificial intelligence in the Republic of Uzbekistan and its organizational and legal framework, it can be noted that artificial intelligence is being implemented in all spheres of our society. At the same time, state bodies responsible for the development and improvement of this sphere have been determined. However, issues such as the protection of intellectual property rights, ensuring the inviolability and security of personal life, and the establishment of moral and spiritual responsibility remain open.

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